

The Presence of Emotion: Designing the Feeling of Being There in Interactive Media Experiences

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Abstract

We discuss key psychological factors relevant to the design of interactive experiences with intended specific emotional impacts: the sense of presence, reality judgement, and awareness of the need for embodied responses. The extent to which a participant experiences a sense of presence (the feeling of being there) within an external environment is particularly important, but is complicated by the fact that mediated experiences are influenced by many other factors, including mental media schemata, which vary across cultures, across historical timescales, and within and between individuals. We expand on these factors in relation to three example interactive environments, each designed to invoke specific emotional responses and types of experience.

Keywords: layers of presence, different emotions, reality judgments, media schemata, virtual environments

Introduction

Emotions can be understood as reactions to situations in which an organism finds itself; as part of our evolved response systems affecting both the body and the mind. Emotions such as the discomfort arising from pain help an organism to avoid damage and increase the chances of survival. When emotions tend to persist or recur over longer periods - of hours and days rather than seconds - they are sometimes called moods. In this paper, we use the term “emotion” rather loosely, to cover both these types of affective response. In this sense, emotion is now well accepted as an important ingredient of successful human-computer interaction (HCI) design. It has arguably always been important in design (for what else distinguishes two equally functional and cost-effective designs?), but as a discipline rooted in the methods and mindset of the cognitive psychology of the 70s and 80s, HCI was slow to accept that affect is as important as mental problem solving - or rather, that emotion and logical problem solving work together in almost all our practical reasoning about the world around us (e.g. Damasio, 1994; 1999).

In the design of HCI, both software and hardware, it is important to keep in mind that not all emotions are equal. As an evolved response system aimed at survival, negative feedback in the form of unpleasant emotional experiences is particularly important. Why? Because, when things are going well, no state-changing response is needed - as with any homeostatic control system. When we are in danger, or hungry, or sexually frustrated, we experience emotions as we respond to make necessary changes to our situation. The “motion” in emotion gets us out of a bad place and into a potentially better one. Arguably, positive emotions are what we feel when things are going fine, when we don’t feel negative emotions! As Pinker (1997; page 374) puts it: “Each human emotion mobilizes the mind and body to meet one of the challenges of living and reproducing in the cognitive niche.” Feeling good does not help us meet challenges; at best it helps us stay put, in a good place. But emotions are not only triggered by the situations we encounter. We can feel emotions just as strongly in imagined or recalled situations as in the present reality, and in response to events we know to be fictional in, say, a film or a novel (Russell, 2003). It follows that any successful and advanced organism must be able to answer the following questions (though not necessarily in this order):

- Is this happening in the world around me, or only in my head?
(answered on the basis of whether I feel present in an external environment)

- Is this likely to be true or is it fiction?
(answered on the basis of a reality judgment)
- Do I need to avoid this, and how urgently?
(answered on the basis of an emotional experience)

By our account, the sense of presence allows us to assess whether a designed experience is happening in the world around us or is a construction created in internal mental space (Riva et al., 2004; Waterworth and Waterworth, 2001). For example, first-person video games usually try to convey the impression that one is physically located in the portrayed scenes, often with others. In contrast, a well-constructed novel may produce equally vivid experiences, but these are felt to exist in the mind of the reader, not in the world around him, and so are not directly shareable. This distinction of feeling the location of an experience reveals the presence mechanism in action.

In the next section, we describe our view of presence in a little more detail, and describe how presence relates to reality judgements and emotional responses. In the following sections, we expand on these factors in relation to three very different interactive environments, each designed to invoke specific emotional responses and experiences: Relaxation Island, the Exploratorium, and the Achievement Room. The work was carried out as part of the EMMA (Engaging Media for Mental Health Applications) project, partially funded by the EU.

Presence, Reality Judgements and Emotional Responses

Reality judgements work in combination with the sense of presence: an experience that evokes high presence is more likely to be judged as real (rather than fictional) than an experience that evokes low presence. Emotional responses reflect bodily changes in the individual, resulting from the core affective mechanism of the organism. Core affect is not concerned with whether events are really happening or are fictions, nor is it concerned with whether the portrayed events are occurring in the world around the person or are mental constructions (Russell, 2003). The physiological responses are the same, and to the extent that the individual is aware of those responses, the emotional experience is the same (we use the word “experience” to mean mental events of which the organism is conscious).

When considering presence it is also important to consider its opposite, absence (Waterworth and Waterworth, 2001), although this has often been ignored in the literature on mediated

presence. It is as important to study the impact emotion has on absence as it is to study its impact on presence, and how the two are related. Our three-layer model of presence (Figure 1) can provide a starting point for predicting whether a design with emotional effects will bring about a certain degree of presence or absence. The three layers are proto-presence, at the sensori-motor level, core presence, at the perceptual level, and extended presence, at the conceptual level.

Figure 1: A 3-layer model of Presence (Riva et al., 2004)

According to this model, the overall presence level depends on how well integrated the cognitive system is to focus on the environment around the individual. Emotion can affect this in several different ways, affecting the top and bottom layers. For example by creating an arousing effect that orientates the individual to attend to the environment (stimulating presence) from the bottom up, presence will be increased. On the other hand, emotion induced at higher levels may increase attention to the environment or reduce it, depending on whether the content is associated with the current environment (presence) or independent of it (absence).

The extent to which mediated experiences evoke a strong feeling of presence, of being bodily situated in a portrayed, surrounding world, changes over time, through the development of changing personal and cultural *media schemata* (Ijsselsteijn, 2003). When the first jumpy, grainy, black and white movies were shown to audiences, the impact was extraordinary: scenes of an approaching train caused members of the audience to run out of the cinema in panic. Today, even wide screens, surround-sound systems and vibrating cinema seats cannot evoke such a dramatic response, although imperfections in the integration of information supplied to the different senses may result in nausea, eyestrain, headaches, or other negative systems of “cybersickness”. Within individuals, media schemata seem to adjust themselves in the light of experience: cinematic special effects that were breathtaking in the early 1980s will have relatively little impact on the same viewer twenty years’ later.

There is also evidence that as our experience of apparently realistic media increases, some of our responses to our evolved psychological mechanisms are being modified. So-called “inverse presence” (Timmins & Lombard, 2005) refers to the phenomenon whereby real events are experienced as computer-mediated. This occurred, for example, when observers saw camera footage of the World Trade Centre tragedy in New York, which many viewers judged to be the result of digital special effects. And in the “uncanny valley” effect, first suggested by Mori (1970), although robots generally increase in judged pleasantness as their apparent humanness increases, a point is reached where the robot becomes so realistic that observers find it repulsive. A similar effect may result from interactive experiences of very high apparent realism, especially those involving human-like avatars.

Within a given time and culture, individual people also vary in their preference and capacity for presence. Since presence is, for us, a reflection of the extent to which an individual is engaged with (and feels able to act in) an external world rather than with an internal world of the imagination, we would expect personality factors that are well known to affect this relation (Eysenk, 1997) to also affect experienced presence. For example, we might expect that extrovert personalities in general prefer higher presence than introvert personalities. Similarly, elderly people might be expected to prefer less presence in interactive situations than the young (Waterworth and Waterworth, 2006).

An important implication of these differences is that the same interactive media will have differing impacts on different individuals, and should be designed either with the user’s presence preferences in mind, or in a way that adapts to this. Since it is often difficult or

impossible to assess personality and other individual characteristics in advance, the best way to address this is to be sensitive to the participant's changing state during the interaction. This sensitivity of the system to the individual can take the form of bio- or psycho-feedback, and thus the approach to individuals can actually be generalisable across individuals. What is detected, though, is not presence, although this might be possible in the future, with instant brain imaging or implants. What we can detect and react to today are physiological and postural responses, reflecting emotional state - which may be in line with presence or opposed to it (absence reflecting emotional engagement with an internal mental construction).

In the remainder of the paper we expand on the discussion of these factors by considering the design of three very different virtual environments, each designed to invoke specific responses based on the interaction of presence, emotions and reality judgements.

The Achievement Room

The Achievement Room was designed for individuals with chronic restricted mobility. Such people are often depressed, partly because of a lack of sensory and emotional stimulation.

The main set up of the Achievement Room consists of either a big back projected screen or a head mounted display, where the individual stands in front of the screen or sits in their bed secluded in a room, with a guitar in the hands. The narrative is that the participant, having failed once before to become a famous rock-star, now has an opportunity of a second chance by giving a concert. First of all the participant hears a voice tell this background story, what is expected of the participant and how to interact in the environment. The individual then finds himself transferred to a virtual stage and gets the opportunity to practice before the actual concert takes place. From a menu the participant is able to choose which song to perform (see Figure 2). Later, the individual finds himself on a virtual stage behind a red curtain and hears the sound of the audience arriving and taking their places in the concert hall. A voice announces the start of the concert and the curtain rises. In front of the participant there is a small screen where he can read the words of the song that he is going to sing, as in a karaoke. The music starts and the participant is expected to strum on the strings and sing along with the background music.

Figure 2: Menu for the Achievement Room

The audience consists of avatars that are programmed to respond to the individual's performance (Figure 3). After the performance a therapist talks to the participant and analyses the concert. If the concert was a failure the participant gets the opportunity to practice again and to give another concert. The audience reaction can be tuned to be more or less demanding.

Figure 3: Screen shot from the Achievement Room

Relaxation Island

Initial results with Relaxation Island were reported in 2005 (Waterworth et al., 2004). In this section we briefly recap on the design of the environment and then report more recent findings that bear on our discussion of emotions in relation to the experienced level of presence.

Relaxation Island was designed as a tropical island where the participant can relax and get rid of his or her worries. Participants arrive by virtual boat on the Island shore. The island is an archetypical tropical paradise, with lush vegetation, a waterfall and a long beach and is surrounded by mountains (Figure 4). It is possible for the participant to explore the island freely at his or her convenience. The participant can also choose among four different areas to learn different relaxation techniques, beach zone 1, beach zone 2, the waterfall and cloud zone.

Figure 4: Relaxation Island.

The aim of the island is to provide a virtual realisation of the kind of imagined spatial location used in standard relaxation techniques such as progressive muscular relaxation and breathing techniques (Bernstein and Borkovek, 1973). In these cases, without a virtual environment, how effectively relaxation is achieved depends on an individual's ability to imagine relaxing scenarios. But with Relaxation Island, it was found that almost all participants are able to relax, independently of their ability to imagine relaxing places

(Freeman et al., 2004). In recent trials with a mobile phone version of the Island, it was found to be significantly more effective for relaxation during a stressful commuter train journey than a New Age video or no relaxation treatments (Preziosa et al., 2005; Villani et al., 2005).

However, the relationship with experienced presence was less obvious, and less simple. In recent trials, what we have found is that i) presence only enhances relaxation for some kinds of relaxation exercise, and ii) over the course of time during a session, the relationship between presence and emotion changes significantly. These findings can be related to our model of presence, and of the relationship between presence, reality judgements and emotional responses.

In some zones, the therapeutic approach is based on ACT (Acceptance and Commitment Theory, see Orsilla and Batten 2005) and in others on the currently very popular CBT (Cognitive Behaviour Therapy, see Bond and Dreyden 2002) approach. In ACT zones, presence enhanced relaxation, whereas in CBT-based zones, presence and relaxation were inversely related - in fact, a sense of presence in the virtual island was a distraction from the relaxation exercises. We can explain this finding in terms of our model of presence. CBT emphasises an internal focus, on thought and imagination. In other words, it stresses a mode of attention that is directed inwards to the self, on the assumption that emotional problems arise from internal sources. The basic idea is to change the way a person internalises, thinks and imagines - all activities that will work against a sense of presence in the surrounding environment, by our account.

In contrast, ACT emphasises an external focus, on the world surrounding the individual and on accepting that world. So in ACT-based zones, the participant is encouraged to empty their mind of thoughts and just be in the external environment - in other words, to be present there in that relaxing place. In CBT-based zones the participant is encouraged to look within and achieve relaxation, essentially by ignoring the surrounding world. The island becomes a distraction, and presence there works against CBT relaxation techniques. When no specific exercises are provided, presence was generally associated with relaxation: tropical islands are relaxing!

The Exploratorium

The Exploratorium was designed as a virtual environment within which participants can explore both places and feelings. The "narrative" it implements is structural rather than story telling. What happens there depends on what the participants do in terms of navigation; if they don't do anything, nothing will happen. Different areas of the Exploratorium present different experiences: scary, normally busy, or very calm. Participants are free to explore the different areas, under their own control. The design goal was to stimulate curiosity, leading to exploration and a consequent sense of control and empowerment, at the same time as the participant experiences, explores and investigates her feelings and emotions. We deliberately chose to limit interaction to navigation. Participants are not able to select or move objects in the space, only to move around using the "body joystick" (see below) as navigation device. We thus emphasise exploration, and it is important that the Exploratorium should evoke enough curiosity in participants for them to become motivated to explore.

It is possible to navigate in the Exploratorium using a variety of devices, such as joysticks, wands, and so on, but the design is more specifically intended for use with the Body Joystick. The Body Joystick consists of a comfortable vest which includes sensors for both body orientation and chest expansion in breathing. It was inspired by the powerful immersive artwork *Osmose* (Davies, 1998). We have adapted the navigation idea by making the vest lightweight and wireless, and we do not use a Head Mounted Display but rather a large back projection screen

The Exploratorium consists of three zones arranged vertically (Figure 5), very loosely based on Dante's *Comedy*: Purgatorio (central zone), Paradiso (top zone) and Inferno (lower zone). The space is arranged in such a way that it relates metaphorically to emotional state. Participants can navigate between different zones within the Exploratorium and encounter surroundings that provoke particular emotional states. The Exploratorium differs from most virtual environments in that it emphasises the vertical dimension of navigation as well as the horizontal. Participants navigate up and down by breathing, and on the horizontal planes by leaning the body. Because of this highly embodied style of interaction, participants potentially have a very vivid sense of presence. The three layers differ in closeness to reality, and in the emotions designed to be invoked.

Figure 5: The three zones of Exploratorium; Paradiso, Purgatorio and Inferno

Early studies showed that the three layers do indeed invoke different emotional responses (Olsson and Waterworth, 2004). Using reported valence and arousal as indicators, Paradiso was judged to be relatively pleasant and calm (though boring), Inferno was unpleasant and stressful, and Purgatorio was more or less neutral (and fairly interesting). In terms of reality judgements, Purgatory was designed to look like the everyday world, whereas the other two zones are more clearly fictional.

General Discussion

With **Achievement Room**, the aim was to provide a sense of achievement and encourage a more positive attitude in the individual. There can be no achievement without challenge, and even if the environment is virtual, the experience of achievement must be real. This brings us back to the view that feeling good is what happens when no longer need to feel bad. Without some negative emotion, a positive emotion has no meaning. We have yet to test the Achievement in clinical trials, although early pilot results confirm its effectiveness.

When visiting **Relaxation Island**, the more real the virtual world was judged to be, the more the three layers of presence come into play. Participants who generally felt high presence were also more likely to feel physical discomfort on the initial boat ride. This is likely to be because of mismatches between core presence and the proto presence layer: the sensori-motor feedback from the body did not match the perceived movement. Discrepancies at the conceptual level, such as a mismatch between memories of tropical islands and the virtual version also led to reduced overall presence.

From a biological perspective, relaxation is at best a weak emotion which, by definition, doesn't lead to action. This is reflected in the time course of presence in relation to relaxation. Early on in the interactive experience, high presence reflects the fact that the participant is engaged with the island and, apart from during CBT exercises, this results in

relaxation. But the more relaxed the person becomes, the less they attend to the island, and so the less they feel present. It seems that once the cognitive system has decided that the person is safe, the participant will stay relaxed so long as there are no distractions - negative emotions - that attract attention to the external world. Without attention being focused on the external environment, relatively low presence will be experienced.

In recent tests with the **Exploratorium** we have found that Paradiso, which is experienced as a pleasant and calm environment, produced a low degree of presence and a high degree of absence, in which participants reported day dreaming or other cognitive activity not related to directly perceiving the environment, quite similar to reaction to Relaxation Island. In the Inferno, on the other hand, which users experienced as both unpleasant and exciting, a high degree of presence and a low degree of absence were reported.

In general, we can see two kinds of relation between reality judgments and the level of presence. Level of core presence contributes to reality judgements; so that if we feel high core presence we are more likely to judge events as real (this mechanism is fooled by VR). Perhaps surprisingly, core presence is not a product of reality judgment, but positive reality judgments will tend to increase extended presence. We can also expect two effects of emotional processes on the level of presence. First, a shift in the level of core affect will activate a higher level of core presence. And easy attribution of this shift to the external world allows a higher level of extended presence.

Conclusions

As a designer one should obviously be aware of the impact a design will have on its user and try to evoke the most suitable emotions and levels of presence for the purpose of the design. In this, it is useful to consider the different levels of the psyche at which emotion may be induced and how they relate to the overall sense of presence. At the lowest layer, emotional responses may include a sensory orientation towards or away from the environment - a very transitory effect, but one which may result in the recruitment of other layers to increase either presence or absence. At the highest layer, the content displayed in an environment will reinforce or inhibit attention to the environment or to other (non-present) conceptualisations. Unless the middle layer, of perception, is aligned to one or both of the other layers, the sense of presence induced will be limited. Since presence reflects bodily and attentional

engagement with an external world, it is an important indicator of the impact of designed media experiences.

As biological organisms, we have no evolved mechanisms that can distinguish the real from the virtual. What we do have are faculties which attempt to separate the external from the internal, the plausible from the implausible, and the pleasant from the unpleasant, all in the service of our survival. These are the mechanisms behind our reactions to interactive designs. In our future research we will be exploring further the relation between presence and emotion in HCI, but with a greater emphasis on everyday memories and mixed reality blends of the real and the virtual. As we increasingly live in and through such blends, the answers to our three “questions of survival” become less and less obvious.

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